
EFFECT OF DIGITAL INFORMATION PRODUCT ON PERFORMANCE OF SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES (SMEs) IN ENUGU STATE

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14780326>

ABSTRACT: The study evaluated the effect of digital information product on performance of SMEs in Enugu State. The specific objectives were to: examine the effect of e-book on the customer retention and ascertain the effect of blogs on the units of output produced by SMEs in Enugu State. Descriptive survey design approach was adopted. A total population of 298 selected staff of the study firms. The whole population was adopted due to small size. Two hundred and sixty-nine (269) staff returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. Data were presented and analyzed by mean score and standard deviation using Sprint Likert Scale. The hypotheses were analyzed using Z – test statistic tool. The study revealed that e-book had significant positive effect on the customer retention, $Z = 7.621 < 9.694$, $P. < .05$. Blogs had significant positive effect on the output $Z = 6.935 < 10.411$, $P. < .05$. The study concluded that e-book and blogs, had significant positive effect on the customer retention and units of output of SMEs in Enugu state. The study recommended among others that the management of SMEs should improve on the use e-book to help integrate video components, quizzes with real-time scoring, and enhance SMEs homework response.

Keywords: Blogs, Digital, e-book, information, performance, product,

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the study

Digital usually refers to something using discrete digits, often binary digits. Digital describes electronic technology that generates stores and processes data in terms of positive and nonpositive states (Yasar, Demir & Taşdemir, 2023). Digital describes electronic technology that generates, stores, and processes data in terms of two states: positive and non-positive. Being digital requires being open to reexamining your entire way of doing business and understanding where the new frontiers of value are. For some companies, capturing new frontiers may be about developing entirely new businesses in adjacent categories; for others, it may be about identifying and going after new value pools in existing sectors, (Dorner & David, 2015).

Digital innovation has become a transformative force across various industries globally, and the banking sector is no exception. In Nigeria, Small and medium Enterprises (SMEs) are increasingly adopting digital technologies to enhance their operational efficiency, customer service delivery, and overall performance (Cărăușu & Lupu, 2023). In recent years, Nigerian Small and medium Enterprises (SMEs) have been leveraging technologies to automate routine tasks, improve decision-making processes, and personalize customer

interactions. Again, technologies have emerged as a critical tool for Nigerian Small and medium Enterprises (SMEs) to harness the vast amounts of customer data generated through digital transactions (Islam et al., 2022). Digital Technology is always connected with obtaining certain result, resolving certain problems, completing certain tasks using particular skills, employing knowledge and exploiting assets. The concept of technology does not only relate to the technology that embodies in the product but it is also associated with the knowledge or information of it use, application and the process in developing the product (Wahab, Raduan & Osman, 2012).

Assessing the performance of organizations has always been of interest to management teams. In organizational context, performance usually is explained as the length to which a member of an organization puts in his efforts towards the achievement of the objectives of that organization. Organizational performance is the ability of an organization to reach its goals and optimize results. It can also be seen as a company's ability to achieve goals in a state of constant change. Organizational performance was looked at from its output. And more than just output of results, the output of financial results (Miles, 2022).

Performance entails monetary and non-monetary; monetary include market share, profitability, and market share, return on equity, assets, investment, and liquidity. Non-monetary measures include decision quality, client satisfaction and efficiency (Kariithi & Kihara, 2017). Performance can also be measured based on subjective information gathered from managers or other key informants, asking them to rate their company's overall performance such as their market share, profitability, innovation efforts, performance of human resource practices, and such other attributes. It has been argued that objective measures are more robust than subjective measures as managers may be reluctant to draw attention to shortcomings and instead may seek to overstate the performance of their organizations (Princewill & Needorn, 2022). So digital information products have come to add to existing performance of small and medium enterprises and boost their content creation. Based on this, the study aimed at evaluating effect of digital information products on the performance of SMEs in Enugu state.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Digital transformation (DT) represents a succession of value-generation activities powered by technology innovation within organizations. It rests on the open sharing and effective usage of data resources to reorganize corporate processes and models, all targeted at increasing user experiences. The digital economy, covering digital technologies and e-commerce, operates as a cornerstone of modern economic operations. It serves a crucial role in generating high-quality economic growth.

However, the poor application of e-book, blogs, podcasts and v logs, lack of time management, poor effective objection handling, lack of motivation, resourcefulness, product knowledge, are issues in digital information products.. Because of lack of physical components the process of value assessment is not straightforward. It is difficult to determine how much the product should cost and what should be its value.

The consequences of the above if not handled might lead to poor average deal size, high Customer acquisition costs, poor Sales revenue and high Sales conversion rates. Based on this the need to study effect of digital information product on performance of SMEs in Enugu state.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study is to evaluate the effect of digital information product on performance of SMEs in Enugu state. The specific objectives are to:

- i. Examine the effect of e-book on customer retention of SMEs in Enugu State.
- ii. Ascertain the effect of blogs on the units of output produced of SMEs in Enugu State.

1.4 Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

- i. What is the effect of e-book on customer retention of SMEs in Enugu State?
- ii. What is the effect of blogs on the units of output produced of SMEs in Enugu State?

1.5 Statement of Hypotheses

The following hypothesis guided the study

- i. E-book has effect on the customer retention of SMEs in Enugu State.
- ii. Blogs has effect on the units of output produced of SMEs in Enugu State

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Digital

Digital means exploiting emerging technologies to create user/customer centric interfaces and data driven decisions, leading to more agile, responsive and competitive business models. Digital describes electronic technology that generates stores and processes data in terms of positive and no positive states. Positive is expressed or represented by the number 1 and no positive by the number 0. Thus, data transmitted or stored with digital technology is expressed as a string of 0s and 1s. Each of these state digits is referred to as a bit; a string of bits that a computer can address individually as a group is a byte, (Yasar, 2023).

2.1.2 Information

Information is a fact, thought or data conveyed or described through various types of communication, like written, oral, visual and audio communications. It is knowledge shared or obtained through study, instruction, investigation or news and you share it through the act of communicating, whether verbally, non-verbally, visually, or through written word, (Information is stimuli that has meaning in some context for its receiver. When information is entered into and stored in a computer, it is generally referred to as data. After processing -- such as formatting and printing -- output data can again be perceived as information. When information is compiled or used to better understand something or to do something, it becomes knowledge, (Techtarget, 2023).

2.1.3 Products

A product is any item or service you sell to serve a customer's need or want. They can be physical or virtual. Physical products include durable goods (like cars, furniture, and computers) and non-durable goods (like food and beverages). Virtual products are offerings of services or experiences (such as education, software, and streaming services). A product may also be a hybrid — including both physical and virtual elements (like a kitchen appliance with its own mobile app), (Aha, 2023). A product is something sold to fulfill a customer's desire or requirement, whether it's tangible or intangible. Physical products can be either durable goods (such as furniture, cars, and electronics) or nondurable goods (such as food and drinks), (Chisellabs, 2024).

2.1.4 Digital Information Products

A digital product refers to a product or service that is primarily based on digital technology, existing in a non-physical or intangible form. Unlike traditional physical products, which are tangible and occupy physical space, digital products are created, distributed, and consumed in a digital environment. This category encompasses a vast array of offerings, ranging from software applications and online platforms to multimedia content and digital services, (Productfolio, 2023). Digital products are intangible goods that exist in a digital format. These include eBooks, music, digital art, software, online courses, and virtual goods in video games. They're typically delivered to customers via download or email, and offer businesses a way to provide value without physical inventory, (Kumar, 2024).

2.1.5 Components of that formed part of the study

2.1.5.1 E-book

E-book, digital file containing a body of text and images suitable for distributing electronically and displaying on-screen in a manner similar to a printed book. E-books can be created by converting a printer's source files to formats optimized for easy downloading and on-screen reading, or they can be drawn from a database or a set of text files that were not created solely for print, (Arthur, 2024). An eBook is a non-editable, reflow able book that is converted to a digital format to be read on any digital device such as computer screens or mobile devices, (Wahl, 2018).

2.1.5.2 Blogs

A blog (short for "weblog") is an online journal or informational website run by an individual, group, or corporation that offers regularly updated content (blog post) about a topic. It presents information in reverse chronological order and it's written in an informal or conversational style, (Maulidina, 2024). A blog is a regularly updated website or web page, and can either be used for personal use or to fulfill a business need. A blog was a personal web log or journal in which someone could share information or their opinion on a variety of topics, (Forsey, 2023).

2.1.6 Performance

Performance is achieved when all efforts are focused towards achieving the set objectives and meeting customer's satisfaction. Objectives and customer satisfaction cannot however be accurately measured. Performance means both behaviors and results. Behaviors are emanating from the performer and turn the performance of an abstract concept into a concrete action. Not being just tools of obtaining some results, behaviors are by themselves outcomes - the product of the physical and cerebral exercise submitted for the execution of tasks and can be judged apart from results (Bourguignon, 2017).

2.1.7 Components of performance that formed part of the objectives of the study

2.1.7.1 Customer Retention

Improving customer service retention means improving the customer experience. Customer retention pertains to a company's ability to turn customers into repeat buyers and prevent them from switching to a competitors (Olson, 2023). Customer retention is the practice of increasing a business's repeat customer rate and extracting additional value from those customers. The goal of customer retention is to ensure a customer makes repeat purchases, is satisfied with a company's services, and does not defect to a competitor. Customer retention is important because it can be greatly influenced by customer satisfaction. Additionally, it reduces the amount of

effort needed to continually reach new customers, which can improve your advertising efficiency and be an important part of your economic strategy (Amazon, 2023).

2.1.7.2 Output

Output is a quantity of goods or services produced in a specific time period (for instance, a year). It is a measure of all the goods and services produced in a given time period by businesses in that industry and sold either to consumers or to businesses outside that industry (Kenton & Robert, 2021). Output can be consumed directly or sold to other businesses for use in producing other output. For example, sugar can be consumed or can be used for further production in making cookies. Output is the efficiency of production of goods or services expressed by some measure. Measurements of productivity are often expressed as a ratio of an aggregate output to a single input or an aggregate input used in a production process, i.e. output per unit of input, typically over a specific period of time. (Kenton & Robert, 2021).

2.1.8 Conceptual Framework of the study

INDEPENDENT VARIABLES

DEPENDENT VARIABLES

Figure 2.1 Linkages of Conceptual Variables

2.2 Theoretical Framework

The study was guided by Viral Loop Marketing Theory by Adam Penenberg in 2008. It describes the way cultural products or networks are led to popularity.

The study was based on Viral Loop Marketing Theory. This theory was developed by Adam Penenberg in 2008, it describes the way cultural products or networks are led to popularity. According to Lane (2017), viral loop marketing theory is a theory that explains how users of a product are its primary marketers. It reveals how a brand's loyal customers spread its messages via continued usage of the brand and incite close associates to also use it. Viral loops are included in companies marketing strategies when their desire is to get their marketing messages to consumers with minimal cost. In most cases, viral loops are considered by small to medium sized businesses because of their significantly smaller budgets compared to bigger businesses (Hassan, 2017). This will help them minimize the amount they spend on advertising, and focus on offering outstanding products instead. Outstanding brands should be the focus because the better the quality of the experience of the users, the quicker and larger the loop spreads. The benefits associated with using viral loops are mainly gotten out of its low cost – high spread factor, which exposes a large audience to a company's marketing message. With this, using viral expansion loops are seen to be convenient ways of handling the struggles marketers go through when picking out the elements of content they expect to go viral. The most vital part of the Viral Loop

marketing theory is the creation of viral expansion loops. These loops are in three categories; User Actions, Notifications and Conversion, they are dependent on their users disseminating these marketing message to their own network.

2.3 Empirical Reviews

2.3.1 E-book and Customer retention

Edet (2021) conducted a study on the impact of social media adoption on customer relationship management. The study proposed three objectives in a bid to solving the problem of the study; this includes to examine the social media adoption stages by SMEs owners in Nigeria; to ascertain whether SMEs owners in Nigeria possess the technology-know-how of social media adoption; to investigate the benefits SMEs owners in Nigeria derives having adopted social media platforms for customer relationship management. In solving the problem of the study, a qualitative approach was employed through a one-on-one interview with 5 selected SMEs owners in Lagos, Nigeria. The response of the interview protocol was analyzed using a thematic approach. The result of the study showed that the SMEs in Nigeria adopt social media in managing customer's relationships; the study also revealed that SMEs owners possess adequate knowledge in utilizing and fully implemented social media technologies in Managing customer's relationships; and that SMEs owners who have adopted social media platforms in managing customer's relationships benefits greatly among which includes expanded sales volume, increased customer-based, customer's loyalty and among others.

Obiekwe and Alozie (2022) Majority of SMEs in Enugu State, Nigeria, are wary of adopting an e-marketing system because they believe it would be expensive to construct, fraudulent, and put them at risk online. In this study, we focus on the financial performance of SMEs in the food/accommodation, manufacturing, retail/wholesale, and transportation service sectors in Enugu State, Nigeria, and analyze the effect of e-marketing on it. The study's specific objectives were to investigate the effects of email marketing, electronic advertising, and electronic payment marketing on the financial performance of SMEs. In order to create a sample that accurately reflected the whole population, the study used a survey research approach to gather data from respondents. 50 SMEs were the target group in Enugu State. Results showed that electronic advertising, email marketing, and electronic payment marketing all significantly impacted firm performance. The survey found that Enugu State SMEs engaged in e-marketing had seen above-average business performance.

Iyke-Ofoedu, Onodugo and Umeh (2022) conducted a study on the effect of internet banking on small and medium enterprises performance in Enugu Metropolis. Specifically this study aims to determine the (i) the effect of internet effectiveness on small and medium enterprises business expansion in Enugu Metropolis, and (ii) the effect of internet convenience on small and medium enterprise quality of job delivery in Enugu Metropolis. The study made use of descriptive survey design. The study used structured questionnaire to obtain data. The population of the study is 650 with sample size of 264. Summary of the study includes: the findings of the study revealed that internet effectiveness has significant effect on small and medium enterprises business expansion in Enugu metropolis ($t - \text{statistics} (38.887) > P - \text{value} (0.000)$), the findings of the study also revealed that internet convenience has significant effect on small and medium enterprise quality of job delivery in Enugu metropolis ($t - \text{statistics} (33.446) > P - \text{value} (0.000)$), and the findings of the study revealed that internet accessibility has significant effect on small and medium enterprise expansion of income base in Enugu metropolis, because internet accessibility enables to conduct banking business over the internet where costs are minimal, since ($t - \text{statistics} (51.826) > P - \text{value} (0.000)$).

Arobo (2022) conducted a study on the value and influence of digital marketing on the competitive participation of small and medium-sized establishments in the business environment. The research would further envisage whether digital marketing can have a substantial effect on the consistent growth and success of SMEs, improve brand recognition, and strengthen customer relationships. This concept has not been previously researched in depth, although there's been related study on social media as it impacts innovation and creativity on SMEs, which indicates that social media can be a very positive strategy on the companies that operate within the context of small and medium-scale Enterprise. This study applies a qualitative research approach which involved five (5) companies which operate as SMEs. Semi-structured interviews were conducted, to help provide the primary data, where respondents to the best of their abilities, provided important information that help conduct this study. Secondary data/information relevant to the study was also gathered through peer-reviewed articles, journals and websites. The study concludes with the view that digital marketing is identified as creative and efficient method of acquiring, growing and maintaining customer relationships. Online platforms such as websites, industry-specific outlets and forums, have been identified to be the most beneficial for SMEs.

Ochinawata and Ochinawata (2023) conducted a study on the impact of digital platforms on online micro and small enterprise development. The research examines how digital platforms enable the creation of online micro and small business in Nigeria and its impact on developing micro and small businesses in Nigeria. The research further explores challenges that are associated with adopting digital platforms for micro and small business development in Nigeria. The research approach adopts a qualitative semi-structured research methodology to explore the research questions and objectives. The methodology consists of a review of the key concepts related to research and, components of appropriate interview questions linked with gaps in knowledge and study objectives. The main findings from the study highlighted the importance of digital skills and social media management as crucial factors that enhance the development and sustenance of micro businesses that adopt online platforms in Nigeria. The findings highlighted the importance of trust and building online customer confidence, thus individuals and entrepreneurs developing small-scale businesses need to ensure customer confidence through feedback and reviews on those platforms. The findings highlighted that most challenges facing micro and small businesses adopting digital platform include trust because there are many fake products and imposters on the internet. Thus, making videos of oneself alongside the product builds customer confidence. This challenge is different from challenges identified in previous kinds of literature such as lack of power supply and inadequate infrastructures.

2.3.2 Blogs and Output

Oguguo, Ajuonuma, Azubuike, Ene, Atta and Oko (2020) conducted a study on the influence of using social media on the academic achievement of senior secondary school students. A sample of 150 students comprising 70 males and 80 females were drawn from five schools and used for the study, this was arrived at through multi-stage sampling procedure. Social Media Questionnaire (SMQ) and Students' Accounting Achievement Proforma (SAAP) were used for data collection. The result showed that students frequently engage in social media in order to make new friends, research about their assignments and source for other educational materials, stay up to dates with latest trends and news. The finding also showed that students spend an average, 2 to 4 hours daily on social media. There was no significant influence of frequency of social media use by students on their mean academic achievements in Accounting; however, gender of students was found to have a significant influence on students' mean academic achievement in Accounting. Students should be guided properly and informed on the vulnerabilities likely to come their way if they fail to appropriately utilize the opportunities that come with having social media platforms

Adeniji (2022) conducted a study on Work engagement has been a major concern to organizations for over three decades, because it is what drives business. For the employee, engagement brings meaningfulness into work, which leads to commitment to the organization and to a sustained relationship with people. Skill variety as a core dimension of Job Characteristics Model is a necessity for bank workers who face a high work demand requiring efforts, talents and diverse skills. The banks in Nigeria play a very important role in the economy of Nigeria, but they are faced with work overload and stress that bother on work engagement. This study was a descriptive one that used the mixed method approach of both quantitative and qualitative research and was carried out on banks in the Lagos metropolis. A total of 438 copies of questionnaires were distributed, and 353 copies were retrieved, and 15 members of senior staff were randomly selected for the interview. Method of analysis was structural equation modeling (Partial Least Square) for the quantitative, while thematic analysis was used for the qualitative. The results of the hypotheses revealed that skill variety significantly influenced physical work engagement (R-square = 0.346); emotional work engagement (R-square = 0.272); and cognitive work engagement (R-square = 0.438). The study concluded that skill variety is significant to work engagement among bankers in Nigeria.

Ezeh, Onah and Ugochukwu, (2022) conducted a study on the Performance Recognition and Employee Output of Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms in Enugu state, Nigeria. The specific objectives were to; examine the relationship between desirable awards and employee quality of work; the relationship between peer recognition and productivity and the relationship between immediate gratification and employee efficiency of Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms in Enugu state, Nigeria. The area of the study comprised of staff of T.U Woods Pharmaceuticals, MICHELLE LABORATORIES, and Juhel pharmaceuticals in Enugu State. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. A total population of 1530 staff was used. The adequate sample size of 307, using Freund and William's statistic formula at 5 percent margin of error. 238 staff returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. Data was presented and analyzed by mean score and standard deviation using Sprint Likert Scale and hypotheses were analyzed using Pearson correlation coefficient (r) statistics tool. The findings observed positive significant relationship between desirable awards and employee quality of work ($r = .221 < .865$); positive significant relationship between peer recognition and productivity ($r = .729 < .868$) and there was positive significant between immediate gratification and employee efficiency of Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms in South-East, Nigeria, ($r = .364 < .809$). The study concluded that Performance Recognition and Employee Output of Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms. The recommended among others that the pharmaceutical firms should like the manufacturing firms get effective reward system that would improve the performance of their staff

Ugwu (2022) conducted a study on the effect of workforce planning on the organizational performance of SMEs in Enugu State, Nigeria. The specific objectives were to evaluate the effect of succession planning on the quality of service of SMEs in Enugu State and determine the effect of leadership development on the profitability of SMEs in Enugu State. The population of the study is three thousand five hundred and eleven (3511) staff of the organizations understudy. The study used the survey approach and stratified random sampling. The primary source was the administration of questionnaire. The adequate sample size of 346 was determined using Freund and William's statistic formula. 331 staff returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. That gave 96 percent response rate. The validity of the instrument was tested using content analysis and the result was good. The reliability was tested using the Pearson correlation coefficient (r). It gave a reliability co-efficient of 0.74 which was also good. Data was presented and analyzed by mean score (3.0 and above agreed while below 3.0 disagreed) and standard deviation using Sprint Likert Scale. The hypotheses were analyzed using Z – test statistics tool. The findings indicated that Succession planning had positive effect on the quality of service of SMEs in Enugu State $Z(95, n = 262) = 7.709 < 10.608, p > 0.05$. And Leadership development had

positive effect on the profitability of SMEs in Enugu State $Z(95, n = 262) = 5.895 < 8.149, p > 0.05$. The study concluded that Succession planning and Leadership development had positive effect on the quality of service and profitability of SMEs in Enugu State.

Adewoye and Adesokan (2023) conducted a study on the application of modern technological facilities for the purpose of enhancing effective communications in the society is referred to as Information and Communication Technology (ICT). Through improvements in technology, Microfinance Banks' (Mfbs) have continued to change their way of operations and service delivery in line with changes in client's needs and sophistications. This study therefore assessed the differences in the effect of factors influencing the usage of ICT in microfinance banks in the south-western Nigeria. Ten microfinance banks in south west Nigeria were purposively selected for the study. Factor analysis technique was employed to analyze the study data. Result revealed that Perceived safety concern (1.813491) and complexity (1.367328) eigenvalues $p = < 0.05$ were the potent factors.

2.4 Gap in Empirical Review

The studies done were carried outside effect of digital information products on the Sales performance of Pharmaceutical firms in Enugu state and did not focus to best of my knowledge on the e-book on the average deal size, blogs on the Customer acquisition costs, podcasts on the Sales revenue and v logs on the Sales conversion rates of pharmaceutical firms In Enugu state. Most of the studies reviewed analysed their data through A purposeful sampling technique, Descriptive statistics and appropriate inferential statistics, Purposive Sampling technique, Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient, Multiple sampling technique, Partial Least Square Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM), Multiple Regression Analysis (MRA) method, Simple linear regression and Pearson correlation coefficient (r) while the present study made use of Z test to test the hypotheses. Therefore, the study aimed at filling this research gap by evaluating the effect of digital information products on the Sales performance of Pharmaceutical firms in Enugu state.

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The study employed descriptive survey design. This method was used because the study employed both quantitative and qualitative data. Moreover, Eze and Okechukwu (2022) opine that this method is used to collect data that aids in accurately describing a research problem.

3.2 Source of Data

Data are classified as either primary or secondary data. The classification was based on the two possible sources: primary source and secondary source. The study made use of primary and secondary data.

3.2.1 Primary Data

A primary data source is the one which the data is collected directly (usually first-hand) by the researcher. For the primary data, the questionnaire was used to collect the data. The primary source was questionnaire.

3.2.2 Sources of Secondary Data

Secondary data is sourced from published materials, internet websites, reports, dailies, text books and so on from the library of the institutions understudy. Sources of secondary can be split into two; parts internal and external sources.

3.3 Area of Study

The area of the study was Enugu State, Nigeria. The following were selected for study; Digital Dreams by Otigba Junctions, Ogui, Roban stores, Besala road, Independence layout, and Game mall, Polo Park. These organizations were selected due to the number of employees and high ethical standard.

3.4 Population of the Study

The populations of the study were two hundred and ninety eight (298) selected employees as shown on table 3.1.

Table 3.1

	SMEs	Employees
1.	Digital Dreams	100
2.	Roban stores	106
3.	Game mall,	92
	Total	298

Source: Researcher, 2024

3.5 Sample Size Determination

The whole population was used due to small number.

3.6. Sampling Technique

The stratified random sampling with a random start was adopted so as to give every unit of the population under study equal opportunity of being selected into sample. The secondary data were collected from firms, journals, publication, textbooks and the internet. Twenty questions (20) in the questionnaire were ranged.

3.7 Instrument for Data Collection

The main instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire. Copies of the questionnaire were administered to the employees of the organisation under study Twenty (20) designed questionnaire was used. The responses generated were used thereafter for data analyses.

3.8 Validity of the Instrument

The instrument was given to two experts from the industry and academia to measure face and content validity. To make sure that the research instruments applied in the work are valid, the research ensured that the instrument measure the concept they are supposed to measure.

3.9 Reliability of the Research Instrument

This was done by administering 20 copies of the prepared questionnaire to the sample of the study. Cronbah's Alpha was used in determining the extent of consistency of the reliability. A Cronbach's alpha value (∞) of greater 0.850 indicated very strong reliability.

Scale: ALL VARIABLES

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	20	100.0
	Excluded	0	.0
	Total	20	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	No. of Items
.85	10

Scale reliabilities were calculated using Cronbach's Alpha; the result obtained was 0.850. This shows that the internal consistency of the scale was good for the purpose of this study because it is greater than 0.85 which was good.

3.10 Method of Data Analyses

Data from the questionnaire were analyzed with the aid of SPSS version 23 using simple, simple percentages, mean and standard deviation. For the 5-point likert scale questions, the scale and decision rule stated below were used in analysing the findings.

Scale: Strongly Agree (SA) -5, Agree (A) - 4, Neutral(N) -3, Disagree (D) -2, Strongly Disagree(SD),1

Decision Rule: If Mean >3.0 , the respondents agree and If mean ≤ 3.0 , the respondents disagree. The decision rule is to accept the null hypothesis if the computed r is less than the tabulated r otherwise rejects the null hypothesis and Z - test was used to test the hypotheses and analyzed with the aid of SPSS.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSES

The chapter presents and analyzes the data collected for the study, its analysis and results of the findings of the study.

4.1 Data Presentation

4.1.1 Effect of e-book on the Sales volume of SMEs in Enugu state

Table 4.2.1.1: Responses on the effect of e-book on the customer retention of SMEs in Enugu state

		5	4	3	2	1	Σ FX	-	SD	Decision
		SA	A	N	DA	SD		X		
1	An eBook earn the email addresses of the potential customers	795	320	96	44	27	1282	4.76		Agree
		159	29	32	22	27	269		1.396	
		59.1	10.8	11.9	8.2	10.0	100%			
2	The ebook is environmentally friendly and it boost sales generation	760	116	105	38	34	1053	4.09		Agree
		152	29	35	19	34	269		1.455	
		56.5	10.8	13.0	7.1	10.5	100%			
3	E book due to cost-effectiveness attracts good number of customers	625	116	207	16	38	1002	3.72		Agree
		125	29	69	8	38	269		1.429	
		46.5	10.8	25.7	3.0	14.1	100%			
4	The use of e-book has interactive experience and several customization options that enhances more sales	690	259	87	12	32	1080	4.01		Agree
		138	64	29	6	32	269		1.337	
		51.3	23.8	10.8	2.2	11.9	100%			
5	Ebook increases the brand visibility, responsibility and recognition	785	184	54	40	28	1091	4.05		Agree
		157	46	18	20	28	269		1.374	
		58.4	17.1	6.7	7.4	10.4	100%			
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								3.742	1.3964	

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 4.1.1., 188 respondents out of 269 representing 69.9 percent agreed that an eBook earn the email addresses of the potential customers with mean score 4.76 and standard deviation of 1.396. The ebook is environmentally friendly and it boost sales generation 181 respondents representing 67.3 percent agreed with mean score of 4.09 and standard deviation of 1.455. E book due to cost-effectiveness attracts good number of customers 154 respondents representing 57.3 percent agreed with mean score of 3.72 and standard deviation of 1.429. The use of e-book has interactive experience and several customization options that enhance more sales 202 respondents representing 75.1 percent agreed with mean score of 4.01 and 1.337. Ebook increases the brand visibility, responsibility and recognition 203 respondents representing 75.5 percent agreed with a mean score of 4.05 and standard deviation 1.374.

4.1.2 Effect of blog on the output of SMEs in Enugu state

Table 4.1.2.1: Responses on the effect of blog on the output of SMEs in Enugu state

		5 SA	4 A	3 N	2 DA	1 SD	ΣFX	- X	SD	Decision
1	Blogs increases the organisational leads and website traffic	530 106 39.4	300 75 27.9	54 18 6.7	74 37 13.8	33 33 12.1	991 269 100%	3.68	1.422	Agree
2	The use of blog helps Stand apart from the competition and attracts wider audience	585 117 43.5	340 85 31.6	54 18 6.7	16 8 3.0	41 41 15.2	1036 269 100%	3.85	1.406	Agree
3	Blogs Create content for other platforms which enhances expansion	570 114 53.5	376 94 34.9	54 18 6.7	12 6 2.2	7 7 2.6	1019 269 100%	3.78	.900	Agree
4	There is building of trust in client relationships and encourages responses through blogs	635 127 47.2	444 111 41.3	39 13 4.8	16 8 3.0	29 29 3.7	1163 269 100%	4.32	.956	Agree
5	Growing email list with blogs enhances productivity	460 92 34.2	428 107 39.8	39 13 4.8	68 34 12.6	23 23 8.6	1018 269 100%	3.78	1.275	Agree
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								3.742	1.3964	

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 4.1.2.1, 181 respondents out of 269 representing 67.3 percent agreed that Blogs increases the organisational leads and website traffic with mean score 3.68 and standard deviation of 1.422. The use of blog helps Stand apart from the competition and attracts wider audience 202 respondents representing 75.1 percent agreed with mean score of 3.85 and standard deviation of 1.406. Blogs Create content for other platforms which enhances expansion 208 respondents representing 88.4 percent agreed with mean score of 3.78 and standard deviation of 1.900. There is building of trust in client relationships and encourages responses through blogs 238 respondents representing 88.5 percent agreed with mean score of 4.32 and 1.956. Growing email list with blogs enhances productivity 199 respondents representing 74.0 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.78 and standard deviation 1.275.

4.2 Test of Hypotheses

4.2.1 Hypotheses One: E-book has effect on e-book on the customer retention of SMEs

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

	An eBook earn the email addresses of the potential customers	The ebook is environmentally friendly and it boost sales generation	E book due to cost-effectiveness attracts good number of customers	The use of e-book has interactive experience and several customization options that enhances more sales	Ebook increases the brand visibility, responsibility and recognition
N	269	269	269	269	269
Uniform Parameters ^{a,b}	Minimum	1	1	1	1
	Maximum	5	5	5	5
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.591	.565	.465	.513
	Positive	.100	.126	.141	.119
	Negative	-.591	-.565	-.465	-.513
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z	9.694	9.268	7.621	8.414	9.572
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

a. Test distribution is Uniform.

b. Calculated from data.

Decision Rule

If the calculated Z-value is greater than the critical Z-value (i.e. $Z_{cal} > Z_{critical}$), reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis accordingly.

Result

With Kolmogorov-Smirnon Z – value ranges from 7.621 to 9.694 and on Asymp. Significance of 0.000, the responses from the respondents as displayed in the table was normally distributed. This affirmed the assertion of most of the respondents that **E-book had significant positive effect on the customer retention of SMEs**

Decision

Furthermore, comparing the calculated Z- value ranges 7.621 to 9.694 against the critical Z- value of .000(2-tailed test at 95percent level of confidence) the null hypothesis was rejected. Thus, the alternative hypothesis was accepted which states that **E-book had significant positive effect on the customer retention of SMEs**

4.2.2 Hypotheses Two: Blogs has effect on blogs on the output of SMEs in Enugu

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Blogs increases the organisational leads and website traffic	The use of blog helps Stand apart from the competition and attracts wider audience	Blogs Create content for other platforms which enhances expansion	There is building of trust in client relationships and encourages responses through blogs	Growing email list with blogs enhances productivity
N		269	269	269	269	269
Uniform Parameters ^{a,b}	Minimum	1	1	1	1	1
	Maximum	5	5	5	5	5
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.423	.501	.635	.635	.490
	Positive	.123	.152	.026	.037	.086
	Negative	-.423	-.501	-.635	-.635	-.490
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		6.935	8.216	10.411	10.411	8.033
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

a. Test distribution is Uniform.

b. Calculated from data.

Decision Rule

If the calculated Z-value is greater than the critical Z-value (i.e. $Z_{cal} > Z_{critical}$), reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis accordingly.

Result

With Kolmogorov-Smirnon Z – value ranges from 6.935 to 10.411 and on Asymp. Significance of 0.000, the responses from the respondents as displayed in the table was normally distributed. This affirmed the assertion of most of the respondents that **Blogs had significant positive effect on the output of SMEs in Enugu State**

Decision

Furthermore, comparing the calculated Z- value ranges 6.935 to 10.411 against the critical Z- value of .000(2-tailed test at 95percent level of confidence) the null hypothesis was rejected. Thus, the alternative hypothesis was accepted which states that **Blogs had significant positive effect on the output of SME in Enugu State**

4.3 Discussion of Findings

4.3.1 E-book has effect on e-book on the customer retention of SMEs

From the result of hypotheses one, the calculated Z- value ranges 7.621 to 9.694 against the critical Z- value of .000 which implies that **E-book had significant positive effect on the customer retention of SMEs. In the**

support of the result in the literature, Olusegu, Olufemi and Olakunle (2020) conducted a study on Online Marketing and the Performance of Small and medium scale enterprises in Ikeja Local Government Area of Lagos state. Our study revealed that the online Marketing affected the performance of SME positively which has allowed youths to be self-employed and created economic growth and regional development. Akujor and Eyisi (2020) conducted a study on the effect of Electronic payment on the performance of SMEs in Nigeria. Findings from the study revealed that E-payment has a negative significant effect on Accountability of SMEs in Nigeria. Also there is a negative insignificant relationship on effect of e-payment on revenue generated by SMEs in Nigeria. Edet (2021) conducted a study on the impact of social media adoption on customer relationship management. The result of the study showed that the SMEs in Nigeria adopt social media in managing customer's relationships; the study also revealed that SMEs owners possess adequate knowledge in utilizing and fully implemented social media technologies in Managing customer's relationships; and that SMEs owners who have adopted social media platforms in managing customer's relationships benefits greatly among which includes expanded sales volume, increased customer-based, customer's loyalty and among others.

4.3.2 Blogs has effect on blogs on the output of SMEs

From the result of hypotheses two, the calculated Z- value ranges 6.935 to 10.411 against the critical Z- value of .000 which implies that **Blogs had significant positive effect on the output of SME in Enugu State. In the support of the result in literature review**, Okundaye, Fan and Dwyer (2019) conducted a study on The purpose of this (qualitative, multiple-case) study is to determine how small-to medium-sized enterprise (SME) leaders in Nigeria use information and communication technology (ICT) adoption as a business strategy to increase profitability and compete globally. The findings of this study may help SME leaders and government leaders address many of the factors inhibiting the adoption of ICT in SMEs in Nigeria. This study may ensure that SMEs are successful and able to create jobs, which in turn may help to promote socioeconomic development through adoption of ICT. Oguguo, Ajuonuma, Azubuiké, Ene, Atta and Oko (2020) conducted a study on the influence of using social media on the academic achievement of senior secondary school students. The finding also showed that students spend an average, 2 to 4 hours daily on social media. There was no significant influence of frequency of social media use by students on their mean academic achievements in accounting; however, gender of students was found to have a significant influence on students' mean academic achievement in accounting.

5.0 SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1. SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

- i. E-book had significant positive effect on e-book on the sales volume of SMEs in Enugu State $Z = 7.621 < 9.694$, $P. < .05$
- ii. Blogs had significant positive effect on blogs on the output of SMES in Enugu State $Z = 6.935 < 10.411$, $P. < .05$

5.2 CONCLUSION

The study concluded that e-book and blogs had significant positive effect on e-book on the customer retention and output of SMEs in Enugu state. A digital product refers to a product or service that is primarily based on digital technology, existing in a non-physical or intangible form. Unlike traditional physical products, which are

tangible and occupy physical space, digital products are created, distributed, and consumed in a digital environment. This category encompasses a vast array of offerings, ranging from software applications and online platforms to multimedia content and digital services. Digital products are intangible goods that exist in a digital format.

5.3 RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the following recommendation were proffered

1. The management of SMEs should make more use e-book to help integrate video components, quizzes with real-time scoring, and homework response questions all in one place.
2. Blogging for business is necessary and should helped to better introduce organisation to new customers, reinforce the relationship with existing clients, and share just about anything one like that relates to the business.

5.4 CONTRIBUTION TO KNOWLEDGE

The studies done were carried outside effect of digital information products on the performance of SMEs in Enugu state and did not focus to best of my knowledge on e-book on the customer retention; blogs on the Output of SMEs in Enugu State. Most of the studies reviewed analysed their data through A purposeful sampling technique, Descriptive statistics and appropriate inferential statistics, Purposive Sampling technique, Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient, Multiple sampling technique, Partial Least Square Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM), Multiple Regression Analysis (MRA) method, Simple linear regression and Pearson correlation coefficient (r) while the present study made use of Z test to test the hypotheses. Therefore, the study aimed at filling this research gap by evaluating the effect of digital information products on the performance of SMEs in Enugu state. .

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